

Oxygen separation via chemical looping of the perovskite oxide $\text{Sr}_{0.8}\text{Ca}_{0.2}\text{FeO}_3$ in packed bed reactors for the production of nitrogen from air[☆]

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ABSTRACT

A redox chemical looping process is investigated as an add-on deoxygenation unit for the production of high-purity nitrogen from air using pressure swing adsorption systems. A material screening study indicated the non-stoichiometric perovskite oxide $\text{Sr}_{0.8}\text{Ca}_{0.2}\text{FeO}_{3-\delta}$ as a promising candidate redox material with fast kinetics and a 75% greater gravimetric oxygen capacity compared to state-of-the-art SrFeO_3 at the desired process conditions. Granules of $\text{Sr}_{0.8}\text{Ca}_{0.2}\text{FeO}_3$ were manufactured and characterised according to their thermodynamic and kinetic redox properties. A lab scale packed-bed reactor was experimentally tested as proof-of-concept and used to validate a convection–diffusion model of mass transfer within the reactor. The model was further applied for scaling up to a production of $1000 \text{ Nm}^3\text{h}^{-1}$ of high-purity nitrogen. The results indicate good performance of the packed-bed configuration and a favourable energy demand compared with existing nitrogen production technologies. The proposed technology could greatly extend the useable oxygen impurity range of pressure swing adsorption systems for nitrogen production.

1. Introduction

Nitrogen is most commonly found in the form of diatomic nitrogen gas (N_2), which is stable due to its triple bond. Nitrogen gas separated from atmospheric air is used across many industries where low chemical reactivity is required. Its inertness makes it an ideal atmosphere for processing substances which would otherwise react with oxygen in the air. Nitrogen gas is also a feedstock for the synthesis of ammonia (NH_3), one of the world's most produced chemicals [1], which also has potential to become a carbon-free energy carrier provided its precursors H_2 and N_2 are produced using renewable energy [2]. The industrial production of ammonia requires high-purity nitrogen with very low oxygen impurities below 3 ppm to avoid catalyst poison [3].

Industrially, there are a number of processes available for separating N_2 from air, including membrane air separation, pressure swing adsorption (PSA), and cryogenic air separation units (ASUs). Membrane air separation is more suitable for low-purity intermediate-scale N_2 production and is not considered further in this discussion. The production of high-purity N_2 is possible with both cryogenic air separation and pressure swing adsorption as can be seen in Fig. 1, but with different capacity ranges and energy demands.

In cryogenic air separation, N_2 and other gas streams are produced by liquefying air and distilling the liquid [5]. The purity of these

streams can surpass 10^6 moles N_2 to O_2 respectively. The technology is mature and widespread, but due to the low operating temperatures, large-scale systems are required to achieve efficient heat management. The double distillation column systems shown in Fig. 1 offer capacities above $8000 [\text{N m}^3 \text{h}^{-1}]$, with an energy demand between 13 and 15 $\text{kJ mol}_{\text{N}_2}^{-1}$. Smaller scale systems only comprise of a single distillation column and tend to offer a lower purity at higher energy demand between 20 and 25 $\text{kJ mol}_{\text{N}_2}^{-1}$.

In pressure swing adsorption (PSA), compressed air is passed through a packed-bed which selectively adsorbs oxygen, water and carbon dioxide to its surface under moderate pressure (7 bar), allowing for a purified N_2 stream at the output [6]. The packed-bed is then regenerated by releasing the pressure, allowing the gases to desorb from the packed-bed. The capacity of a given PSA system decreases with increasing purity, as the packed-beds need to be regenerated more frequently leading to more compressed air dumped to the atmosphere [4]. While PSAs can be operated at high-purity, the energy demand exponentially increases with purity, while the capacity exponentially decreases, as seen in Fig. 1.

For large-scale operations ASUs are economic, but as the capacity and purity requirements decrease, systems based on pressure swing adsorption can become more suitable [5]. While the energy demand

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Fig. 1. Production capacity vs. N_2 purity $\left(\frac{1}{x_{O_2}}\right)$ for commercially available N_2 production units. Energy demand is also displayed by the colour map ranging from 12 $\text{kJ mol}_{N_2}^{-1}$ to 75 $\text{kJ mol}_{N_2}^{-1}$. For cryogenic ASUs, the data is shown for the single column (SC) and double column (DC) low pressure N_2 production systems offered by Cryogenmash. For PSA the data is based on systems offered by Genoron and Hygear, and data from chapter 2 of *Industrial Gas Processing* [4]. See Section 1 of the ESI for full details.

of an ASU is lower than PSA, the capital costs, size, complexity, and inflexibility of these systems can outweigh the lower energy demand. Because of this PSA is still commonly used. The capacity of PSA systems at high-purity can be improved by adding an oxygen separation unit after the PSA to remove trace oxygen. This can be achieved using a copper/copper oxide packed-bed which absorbs the oxygen in an oxidation reaction [6]. The packed-bed can then be regenerated by reducing the copper oxide under hydrogen, and repeatedly used in a chemical looping process. Very low oxygen impurities are achievable via this method, but due to the need for hydrogen this process is no longer commonly available.

The substitution of this hydrogen driven chemical looping cycle with a temperature and pressure swing cycle offers an interesting alternative trace oxygen separation process. For example the reversible reduction and oxidation of the perovskite oxide $\text{SrFeO}_{3-\delta}$, has been studied for air separation processes including nitrogen production [7,8] and oxygen production [9].

As an add on oxygen separation unit for the PSA systems, this can bring two main benefits, namely; a reduced energy demand at high-purity, and an increased capacity at high-purity [10]. The redox material selectively removes only the oxygen, with an energy demand that scales with the moles of O_2 to be separated, as opposed to the exponential increase with N_2 purity seen for PSA.

The proposed combined system can be seen in Fig. 2, where a PSA system is used to produce N_2 with a purity between 99% and 99.9%. This gas is then heated by a heat exchanger and flows into one of two packed-beds of perovskite, where the gas is purified to ppm level O_2 impurities via oxidation of the bed. The other bed would simultaneously undergo reduction via heating and vacuum pumping. The PSA unit outputs gas at 7 to 11 bar. If pressures above this are required, a compressor could be placed after the PSA system, with greater pressures benefiting the oxygen absorption process.

In this study we investigate this combined process. Firstly, we perform a materials screening study to select a perovskite with a greater oxygen storage capacity than $\text{SrFeO}_{3-\delta}$, which highlighted $\text{Sr}_{0.8}\text{Ca}_{0.2}\text{FeO}_{3-\delta}$ as a promising candidate. Granules of $\text{Sr}_{0.8}\text{Ca}_{0.2}\text{FeO}_{3-\delta}$ are produced and experimentally characterised according to their redox thermodynamics, kinetic performance and cycle stability. A lab-scale

packed-bed reactor experiment is then performed over a range of operating conditions. A packed-bed reactor model based on the materials characterisation is then tested and validated. Finally, the model is applied to pre-design a large-scale system, and to perform an energy balance for comparison to alternative technologies.

2. Materials screening

The materials redox properties are key to designing the redox reactor units, where selecting more favourable materials can lead to smaller packed-beds operating at less demanding temperatures. Ideally, the materials redox thermodynamics should allow for significant reduction at relatively low temperatures (preferably $T \leq 873$ K), allowing conventional stainless steels to be used in the reactor construction. Similarly, the material must undergo rapid re-oxidation at lower temperatures, while also having an oxygen activity capable of absorbing oxygen at very low partial pressures. $\text{SrFeO}_{3-\delta}$ exhibits non-stoichiometric reduction behaviour [11–13], undergoing significant reduction at 873 K, and exhibiting rapid oxidation kinetics at 550–650 K [14]. $\text{SrFeO}_{3-\delta}$ can also be produced from Fe_3O_4 and SrCO_3 , which are low cost abundant materials. For this reason it has been the subject of many previous studies on air separation processes [8,9,15].

There is room for improvement upon $\text{SrFeO}_{3-\delta}$, in terms of both thermodynamics and kinetics. A process model indicated that the oxygen bond strength of SrFeO_3 is suitable to achieve oxygen impurities well below ppm levels [10]. One could therefore consider materials with a lower enthalpy of reduction, allowing for a greater oxygen storage capacity in the oxide at lower temperatures [16]. Examples of such materials include perovskites containing cobalt such as $\text{Y}_{0.5}\text{Ba}_{0.5}\text{CoO}_{3-\delta}$ [17], and $\text{Sr}_{0.8}\text{Ca}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.6}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ [18], which can offer more than double the oxygen storage capacity under certain process conditions. On the other hand, they may not be suitable for achieving high-purity N_2 due to their lower oxygen bond strength. The substitution of cobalt into $\text{SrFeO}_{3-\delta}$ has also been shown to improve the oxidation kinetics at lower temperatures [14,18]. While the benefits of using Co-based perovskites are clear, the cost of cobalt is very high due to an increasing demand in battery applications and a constricted supply chain [19]. We therefore rule out cobalt containing perovskites and consider other routes of decreasing the enthalpy of reduction.

There have also been a number of material screening studies for this application, which consider perovskites in general [20–22], and many recent studies which are focused on modifying SrFeO_3 by ion substitution giving perovskites of the form $\text{A}_x\text{Sr}_{1-x}\text{B}_y\text{Fe}_{1-y}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ [15,23–25]. Besides from the addition of cobalt, the enthalpy of reduction has also been decreased by the substitution of strontium with both calcium [18,24,26], and barium [15]. Substituting calcium in place of strontium appears to be very promising for increasing the oxygen storage capacity at temperatures below 873 K [18,24,26]. Therefore we focus here on materials of the form $\text{Sr}_{1-x}\text{Ca}_x\text{FeO}_{3-\delta}$, with $x = 0, 0.1$ and 0.2 .

2.1. Granule production

A method for producing granules was adapted from previous work [27]. A slurry made by combining the powdered precursor materials Fe_3O_4 , SrCO_3 and CaCO_3 with an organic binder and an organic solvent, is dripped from a needle into a water bath. Upon contact with water the solvent is dissolved while the water-insoluble binder is left behind. The granules are dried in air and then placed in a furnace. They are first slowly heated to 300 °C to remove the binder, followed by a high-temperature calcination at 1200 °C for 15 h to induce the solid-state reaction of the precursors to the perovskite $\text{Sr}_{1-x}\text{Ca}_x\text{FeO}_{3-\delta}$. A full description of this granule production process is given in Section 2 of the ESI. A photograph of the produced granules as well as SEM images of the outer surface and inner structure can be seen in Fig. 3, where the material appears to have a closed pore structure. Due to the high viscosity of the precursor slurry, the fall time between the needle and the water was insufficient to allow the slurry droplet to turn completely spherical and the resulting droplets had a small tail.

Fig. 2. A simplified diagram of the proposed system composed of a PSA unit to bring the O_2 concentration down to less than 1% and then a pair of redox packed-beds for further oxygen removal. The dashed lines are connections with no flow at that point in the cycle. The dotted elements are optional depending on the specific configuration.

Fig. 3. Left: A photograph of the granules produced. Centre: An SEM image of the outer surface of a granule. The grains appear densely packed with some small pores visible. Right: An SEM image of the inner structure of a fractured granule. The inner structure appears to also have densely packed perovskite grains with some small pores visible.

2.2. Thermogravimetric analysis

The oxygen storage performance of the materials were tested using a thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA, Netzsch STA 409 CD). The TGA has three mass flow controllers (MFCs) which were connected to Ar (99.995%), synthetic air (20% O_2 , 80% N_2) and O_2 (99.999%). The gasses were mixed to get different O_2 concentrations in the range 1%–100%. The volume flow rates were calibrated with a flow meter (MesaLabs Defender 530+L rev. A) prior to sample measurements.

For the material screening tests, approximately 200 mg of granules were loaded into the TGA. The granules were first reduced at a temperature of 873 K in a 1% O_2 atmosphere, followed by re-oxidation at 623 K in a 5% O_2 atmosphere. Argon was flowed over the sample to avoid premature oxidation during the cool down. The performance was compared based on the re-oxidation profile which is shown in Fig. 4. A baseline measurement was made for $SrFeO_3$ granules. Also plotted for comparison is a previous kinetic and thermodynamic model of a larger 8×4 mm $SrFeO_{3-\delta}$ pellet [10]. A four-fold increase in reaction kinetics under the same conditions can be seen for the granules relative to the larger pellet, which is likely due to the shorter diffusion length to the interior of the granules. $Sr_{0.9}Ca_{0.1}FeO_{3-\delta}$ shows a modest improvement in oxygen capacity of 15% relative to $SrFeO_{3-\delta}$. The best performance is seen for $Sr_{0.8}Ca_{0.2}FeO_{3-\delta}$ which shows an improved oxygen storage capacity of almost 75% relative to $SrFeO_{3-\delta}$, with a very small regression in oxidation kinetics.

A possible explanation for the increase in oxygen capacity can be linked to the change in tolerance factor t of the crystal, due to the smaller ionic radius of Ca^{2+} relative to Sr^{2+} [22]. This substitution

Fig. 4. The mass increase vs. time for the re-oxidation of $Sr_{1-x}Ca_xFeO_{3-\delta}$ granules, with $x = 0, 0.1$ and 0.2 . The granules were first reduced and then re-oxidised isothermally at 623 K in a 5% O_2 atmosphere.

of calcium contracts and strains the crystal lattice [28], which could in turn decrease the binding energy of oxygen, and the enthalpy of reduction. The increased oxygen storage agree with a previous study by Luongo et al. where the oxygen storage capacity of $Sr_{0.8}Ca_{0.2}FeO_{3-\delta}$ was approximately double that of $SrFeO_{3-\delta}$ under temperature controlled reduction below 773 K as seen in Fig. 2 of their work [24]. Similarly Dou et al. also observed significant increases in oxygen storage capacity

Table 1
The results of a Rietveld refinement for the PXRD measurements.

Sample	Space group	$a = b$ [Å]	c [Å]	ρ [kg m ⁻³]
SrFeO _{3-δ}	$I4/mmm$	10.9373(1)	7.7024(1)	5464
Sr _{0.8} Ca _{0.2} FeO _{3-δ}	$I4/mmm$	10.9054(1)	7.6765(1)	5237

Table 2
The density of Sr_{0.8}Ca_{0.2}FeO_{3- δ} as well as calculated density and void fraction of the granules.

Material density	ρ_{SCF}	5237	[kg m ⁻³]
Granule density	$\rho_{granule}$	3340 ± 330	[kg m ⁻³]
Void fraction	$\epsilon_{granule}$	0.35 ± 0.035	[-]

for both temperatures in the range 673–823 K and p_{O_2} and oxygen partial pressures of 0.01–0.2 bar as seen in Fig. 3 of their work [18].

3. Characterisation of Sr_{0.8}Ca_{0.2}FeO_{3- δ} granules

In this section we characterise the material Sr_{0.8}Ca_{0.2}FeO_{3- δ} in terms of phase composition, thermodynamics across a range of temperature and p_{O_2} conditions, as well as oxidation kinetics at temperature in the range 598–648 K. This characterisation can then be implemented in a packed-bed model of Sr_{0.8}Ca_{0.2}FeO_{3- δ} granules and experimentally validated in a lab-scale reactor.

3.1. Crystal structure and granule density

The phase composition of both the SrFeO_{3- δ} and Sr_{0.8}Ca_{0.2}FeO_{3- δ} samples were determined using powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD). The granules were ground down to powder and then scanned in a powder diffractometer (Rigaku SmartLab) using a Cu-K α radiation source ($\lambda = 1.5406$ Å) in 2θ reflection geometry from 10–90°, with a step size of 0.01°. The resulting PXRD patterns showed high phase purity with no detectable side phases. The peaks matched that of the tetragonal perovskite phase with space group $I4/mmm$ [29,30]. Rietveld refinement of the data was performed using *FullProf Suite* software, and the structural model for Sr₈Fe₈O₂₃ (PDF 01-070-5776) [29]. The data and fit are given in Figures S2 and S3 of the ESI, with the main results of the fit shown in Table 1.

The structure of Sr_{0.8}Ca_{0.2}FeO_{3- δ} synthesised in air has previously been reported by Luongo et al. as cubic [24]. However, the data reported by Luongo et al. at large angles $2\theta > 60^\circ$ also appear to have peak splitting which is not consistent with the cubic structure, suggesting they also had a tetragonal phase. The unit-cell parameters show a contraction of the unit cell of Sr_{0.8}Ca_{0.2}FeO_{3- δ} relative to SrFeO_{3- δ} which can be explained by the smaller atomic radius of Ca²⁺ relative to Sr²⁺.

The material density of Sr_{0.8}Ca_{0.2}FeO_{3- δ} was determined from the XRD unit-cell volume to be 5237 kg m⁻³. The granules themselves are not dense but contain some void fraction. The density of the granules was estimated via mass and volume measurements (see Section 3.1 of the ESI). Finally, the granule density and the material density of Sr_{0.8}Ca_{0.2}FeO_{3- δ} can be used to determine the granule void fraction, with the resulting figures given in Table 2.

3.2. Thermodynamic analysis

Upon cooling in air during the granule synthesis the material Sr_{0.8}Ca_{0.2}FeO_{3- δ} does not attain a fully oxidised state, i.e. $\delta \neq 0$. The non-stoichiometry of the synthesised granules will depend on the atmosphere and the cooling rate at the end of the synthesis. The initial oxygen non-stoichiometry of the synthesised materials was determined via mass measurements of both the precursors and the final synthesised perovskites, together with the known stoichiometry of the solid-state synthesis reaction. Powder mixtures of the precursors were thoroughly

Table 3

Equilibrium non-stoichiometry model parameters for Eq. (3), determined via a non-linear least squares fit of the data shown in Fig. 5 as well as the standard deviation errors. The fit had an $R^2 = 0.989$.

$a = 0.000324 \pm 0.000030$	$d = 0.000229 \pm 0.00058$
$b = -0.133 \pm 0.023$	$e = -0.0783 \pm 0.23$
$c = -0.197 \pm 0.44$	$f = 0.00444 \pm 0.0057$

mixed together, weighed, and calcined under the same conditions as the granules. With this method, the non-stoichiometry of the produced granules was determined to be $\delta_0 = 0.157$. This value is very close to the room temperature non-stoichiometry of Sr_{0.8}Ca_{0.2}FeO_{3- δ} samples synthesised in air from a previous study of $\delta_0 = 0.15$, determined via idiometric titration [24].

The as synthesised perovskites granules were then brought to a reference state of 500 °C in a 20% oxygen atmosphere and the mass change was used to determine absolute non-stoichiometry at this reference state.

Thermogravimetric analysis was then used to determine the equilibrium oxygen non-stoichiometry of Sr_{0.8}Ca_{0.2}FeO_{3- δ} in the temperature range 623–973 K and with p_{O_2} in the range 0.004 - 1 bar. This was achieved by placing approximately 300 mg of granules in the TGA and varying the temperature and gas feed composition. Equilibrium data points were extracted when the mass had stabilised for a fixed temperature and partial pressure. The partial pressures were determined from the gas mixture composition and verified via gas analysis with an Agilent micro GC. The sample was regularly returned to the reference state at 500 °C in a 0.2 bar oxygen atmosphere which is used to zero the data, and remove any mass drift in the TGA. In fact, the system showed almost negligible drift. In addition, a blank TGA scan with the same program was performed to correct for buoyancy and gas flow effects. The non-stoichiometry value δ , can then be calculated from the mass changes measured in the TGA using the formula

$$\delta = \frac{\Delta m}{m} \frac{M_{sample}}{M_O}, \quad (2)$$

where Δm is the mass change relative to the reference state, M_O is the atomic mass of oxygen and M_{sample} is the molar mass of the perovskite at the reference state. The results of this analysis can be seen in Fig. 5, with the raw data and further details of the analysis given in Section 4 of the ESI.

An empirical analytical function was fit to the measured equilibrium non-stoichiometry with varying temperature and oxygen partial pressure. The function is given by the equation,

$$\delta(T, p_{O_2}) = aT + b + \log(p_{O_2}) \left(c + dT + e \arctan((T - 750 \text{ K})f) \right) \quad (3)$$

with the results of the fit given in Table 3.

The model is most accurate at low temperature, particularly in the temperature range 623–673 K where the reactor will operate during oxidation as seen in Fig. 5. At the proposed oxidation conditions of 623 K and $p_{O_2} = 0.004$ bar, the model gives $\delta_{model} = 0.148$ versus the measured value of $\delta_{measured} = 0.151$. At the reduction conditions 873 K and 0.004 bar_{O₂} the model gives $\delta_{model} = 0.321$ versus $\delta_{measured} = 0.327$. At these oxidation and reduction conditions, the oxygen storage capacity from the model is just 1.7% greater than the measured oxygen capacity.

Based on the equilibrium measurements the enthalpy of reduction can be extracted via the Van't Hoff method, as it is commonly applied to such non-stoichiometric oxides [31,32], based on the equilibrium condition;

$$\Delta g_O(\delta) = \Delta h_O^\circ(\delta) - T \Delta s_O^\circ(\delta) + \frac{1}{2} RT \log\left(\frac{p_{O_2}}{p^\circ}\right) = 0 \quad (4)$$

where Δg_O is the partial molar change in Gibbs free energy of the reversible redox reaction, Δh_O° is the partial molar change in enthalpy at standard pressure, and Δs_O° is the partial molar change in entropy

Fig. 5. Equilibrium non-stoichiometry δ vs. the oxygen partial pressure p_{O_2} , plotted at a range of temperatures, where points are the experimentally measured data and the lines show the fitted equilibrium model.

at standard pressure. These parameters are assumed to depend on δ and the subscript O indicates they are per mole of atomic oxygen. The method was applied at three fixed non-stoichiometry values in the range $\delta = 0.15$ – 0.2 , where the samples had reached equilibrium and showed a clear linear dependence on Van't Hoff plots of $\frac{1}{2} \ln(p_{O_2})$ vs. $\frac{-1}{RT}$ (see ESI Section 4.2 and 4.3). The resulting enthalpies of reduction per mole of atomic oxygen were $\Delta h_O^\circ = 56.5$, 57.9 and 58 kJ mol^{-1} at $\delta = 0.15$, 0.174 and 0.185 respectively. The average of these values $\Delta h_O^\circ = 57.5 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ was used as the enthalpy of reduction when modelling the process. This average value for $\text{Sr}_{0.8}\text{Ca}_{0.2}\text{FeO}_{3-\delta}$ is lower than the enthalpy of reduction for $\text{SrFeO}_{3-\delta}$ determined via the same method in a previous study, which was in the range $\Delta h_O^\circ = 65$ – 80 kJ mol^{-1} in the low temperature range [8]. The decrease is in agreement with previous studies which showed the enthalpy of reduction decreasing with increasing Ca substitution for Sr at temperatures below 873 K [18, 24, 26], and it explains the increased oxygen storage capacity. Luongo et al. also applied the Van't Hoff method and determined the enthalpy of reduction for $\text{Sr}_{0.8}\text{Ca}_{0.2}\text{FeO}_{3-\delta}$ to be in the range $\Delta h_O^\circ = 18$ – 32 kJ mol^{-1} [24]. Duo et al. applying the same method at temperatures in the range 773 – 973 K obtained a value of $\Delta h_O^\circ = 24.4 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ [18]. These values are significantly lower than that obtained in this work of $\Delta h_O^\circ = 57.5 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$. However, it should be noted that in both of these studies the Van't Hoff plots of the data do not show a good linear dependence for constant δ (see Figure S13 in Luongo et al. and Figure S7 in Duo et al.), and that Luongo et al. also measure a much lower enthalpy of reduction for $\text{SrFeO}_{3-\delta}$ relative to well established results in the literature [30, 33]. Jai et al. measured values in the range $\Delta h_O^\circ = 30$ – 40 kJ mol^{-1} for $\text{Sr}_{0.8}\text{Ca}_{0.2}\text{FeO}_{3-\delta}$ in the temperature range 673 – 773 K via oxygen partial pressure swing experiments using differential scanning calorimetry combined with TGA mass changes. However, again the enthalpy change in Jai et al. for $\text{SrFeO}_{3-\delta}$ are also significantly lower than those in the literature measured by the more accurate drop calorimetry method [33], raising concerns about the accuracy of the results. Given the broad disagreement in results we simply take the values determined here over those in the literature.

3.3. Kinetic analysis

The performance of a packed-bed reactor for oxygen separation depends strongly on the reaction kinetics. The reduction takes place at 873 K , with rapid reaction rates that appear to be limited by heat and mass transfer. The oxidation takes place at lower temperatures and under low p_{O_2} , where the reaction kinetics are the limiting factor. Here we use a TGA system to perform an isothermal relaxation kinetic study

Table 4

Kinetic model parameters for Eq. (6), determined via numerical fits of the data shown in Fig. 6. The errors are the standard deviations found for a range of fixed X values in the case of E_a and a range of fixed p_{O_2} in the case of m .

Parameter	Value	Units
E_a	84 ± 9	$[\text{kJ mol}^{-1}]$
k_0	5.3×10^4	$[\text{mol}^{-1} \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}]$
n	1	[-]
m	0.8 ± 0.1	[-]

for the oxidation of $\text{Sr}_{0.8}\text{Ca}_{0.2}\text{FeO}_{3-\delta}$ granules at $p_{O_2} = 0.01$ – 0.2 bar and $T_{\text{ox}} = 593$ – 653 K .

For the relaxation study, approximately 300 mg of granules were first reduced at a temperature of 873 K under a gas flow of 100 ml/min with $p_{O_2} = 0.01$ bar. They were then cooled to the desired temperature under a low flow of argon of 30 ml/min , and the temperature is given time to stabilise. The argon flow was then changed to 200 ml/min for 5 min , before the final switch to the oxygen carrying gas with the same flow rate of 200 ml/min and an oxygen mole fraction in the range $x_{O_2} = 0.01$ – 0.2 . The mass then increased with the oxidation reaction, with total mass changes of around 6 mg or 2% relative mass. To analyse the data we first rule out mass transfer limitations, and also omitted data measured during the gas switching phase. We then apply the iso-conversional method in order to isolate the dependence on temperature, and oxygen concentration [34]. Finally we fit the kinetics with a suitable model that depends on temperature, oxygen concentration and conversion extent. The raw TGA data and full details of the kinetic analysis applied are given in Section 5 of the ESI.

Fig. 6 shows the kinetic data, with the conversion extent X , a unit-less parameter given by,

$$X = \frac{\delta_0 - \delta(t)}{\delta_0 - \delta_{\text{eq}}(T, p_{O_2})} \quad (5)$$

where δ_0 is the non stoichiometry at $t = 0$, and $\delta_{\text{eq}}(T, p_{O_2})$ is the equilibrium non-stoichiometry at the given oxygen partial pressure and temperature. The rate of reaction can be seen to increase with both increasing oxygen mole fraction and increasing temperature. This reaction rate can also be seen to decrease with increasing X which is typical of such reactions [14]. To model the kinetics we chose a simple kinetic model given by,

$$\frac{dX}{dt} = k C_{O_2}^n (1 - X)^m \quad [\text{s}^{-1}] \quad (6)$$

where the rate constant k was assumed to have an Arrhenius dependence,

$$k = k_0 \exp\left(\frac{-E_a}{RT}\right) \quad [\text{mol}^{-1} \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}]. \quad (7)$$

Fitting the dependence on oxygen concentration at constant temperature and conversion extent, yielded $n = 0.9$. However, in the later packed-bed model this was seen to overestimate the kinetics at low oxygen concentrations. Therefore, the power dependence was simply fixed at $n = 1$, so that the rate is directly proportional to the oxygen concentration. The parameter m was then fixed by fitting the constant temperature data in the left graph of Fig. 6, while the activation energy E_a was determined via the iso-conversional method applied to the data in the right graph of Fig. 6 [34]. Finally k_0 was fixed to best fit of the data in both graphs in Fig. 6. The activation energy was determined at the lowest oxygen partial pressure of $p_{O_2} = 0.01$ bar, as the process should operate at low oxygen concentrations. The model fit parameters are given in Table 4.

3.4. Cycle stability tests

The performance of the $\text{Sr}_{0.8}\text{Ca}_{0.2}\text{FeO}_{3-\delta}$ granules over a total of 500 consecutive redox cycles was tested by TGA. A mass of 296.8 mg of granules was loaded in the TGA and repeatedly heated to 873 K with a heating rate of 20 K/min and with a gas flows of 90 ml/min

Fig. 6. Left: Extent of reaction X vs. time for the oxidation at a temperature of 623 K oxygen mole fractions in the range 0.2–0.01 showing experimental data and the model given in Eq. (6). Right: Extent of reaction X vs. time for the oxidation at various temperatures with an oxygen mole fraction of 0.01, showing experimental data and the fit model.

Fig. 7. Relative mass change vs. time for the oxidation of 296.8 mg of granules at 623 K in a 10% oxygen atmosphere during the 1st cycle and at intervals up to the 500th cycle.

argon and 10 ml/min synthetic air giving a 2% oxygen atmosphere, followed by cooling to 623 K at 15 K/min in 100 ml/min synthetic air. In this way the materials were continuously cycled both in temperature and non-stoichiometry. Isothermal oxidations were then performed at intervals to test the effect of the cycles on both the total oxygen storage capacity and the kinetic performance. The isothermal oxidation scans were performed at 623 K following the same procedure used in the kinetic study, and 10% oxygen atmosphere. The total mass increase for the first oxidation was $\Delta m = 6.28$ mg, with the result normalised with respect to this value to give relative changes.

The results are plotted in Fig. 7, with some of the raw TGA data can be seen in Figure S11 in the ESI. After the first 50 cycles the kinetic performance of the granules improved slightly relative to the 1st cycle. This could be due to the cycling improving the homogeneity of the sample or removing surface contaminants such as carbonates that may have formed during the cooling of the samples in air. From the 50th to the 500th cycle there is a small amount of degradation seen in both the later stages of the oxidation kinetics and the total mass change. The total mass change after 60 min of oxidation saw a 2% decrease from the 1st cycle to the 500th cycle. Upon removing the granules from the TGA, there was no apparent damage to the naked eye, but SEM scans did reveal the formation of fractures in the granules surface (see Figure S12 in the ESI). The changing temperature and oxygen non-stoichiometry can result in phase transitions in these materials [29], and indeed a phase change to brownmillerite was observed for $\text{Sr}_{0.8}\text{Ca}_{0.2}\text{FeO}_{3-\delta}$ when reduced in nitrogen at 873 K [24]. The fractures observed are likely the result of the aggressive cycling conditions employed combined with the stresses induced by the reduction. This may be less of an issue in a scaled up system with less rapid cycling conditions.

Overall, the granules in this study showed very good oxygen storage performance stability over many consecutive cycles. The high performance is likely due to the fact that the maximum operating temperature of 873 K is far below the annealing temperature used to produce the granules of 1473 K. Similar results have been observed for the perovskite $\text{Sr}_{0.8}\text{Ca}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.6}\text{O}_3$, which was subjected to 2000 redox cycles without a significant drop in performance [18].

3.5. Reactor model

A 1-D transient mass transfer model of the packed-bed reactor was developed based on the equilibrium and kinetic models, and implemented using the finite element method software *COMSOL*. The beds were taken as cylindrical and the following assumptions were made to simplify the model:

1. Radial and axial symmetry of solution for the cylindrical packed-bed.
2. Gravitational effects and preferential flow paths are neglected.
3. The volume of the pellets does not change with temperature or non-stoichiometry.
4. No significant pressure drop occurs along the bed.
5. The kinetic model is valid at low oxygen partial pressures.

The bed was discretised by a 1-D mesh along the axis of the bed with a resolution of 0.1 mm. Initially the system is treated as isothermal which matches the packed-bed experiments where the temperature is maintained constant by a PID system. Mass transfer is then modelled using the convection diffusion equation for dilute oxygen gas in the nitrogen flow with a source term for the oxidation reaction, given by,

$$\varepsilon_{bed} \frac{\partial C_{O_2}}{\partial t} = -\frac{\partial(u_s C_{O_2})}{\partial x} + D_{eff} \frac{\partial^2 C_{O_2}}{\partial x^2} + 0.5 C_{SCF} \left(\frac{\partial \delta}{\partial t} \right) \quad (8)$$

where ε_{bed} is the void fraction of the packed-bed, C_{O_2} is the local oxygen concentration, u_s is the superficial velocity of the gas in the bed, D_{eff} is the effective diffusion coefficient of the O_2 in N_2 , and C_{SCF} is the concentration of the oxide $\text{Sr}_{0.8}\text{Ca}_{0.2}\text{FeO}_3$ in the packed-bed. This equation is valid as long as the reactant gas is dilute compared to the carrier gas, which is valid for this application.

The source term was implemented using the non-stoichiometry equilibrium model for $\text{Sr}_{0.8}\text{Ca}_{0.2}\text{FeO}_{3-\delta}$ given by Eq. (3) and the kinetic model according to Eq. (6), with the addition of a pressure dependence. The resulting ODE was solved independently for each element and given by,

$$\frac{d}{dt} \delta(t) = k_0 \exp\left(\frac{-E_a}{RT}\right) \left(\frac{p}{p^0}\right)^n C_{O_2} (\delta_0 - \delta(t))^m (\delta_0 - \delta_{eq}(p_{O_2}, T))^{1-m} \quad (9)$$

where δ_0 is the initial non-stoichiometry, $\delta(t)$ is the current non-stoichiometry and $\delta_{eq}(p_{O_2}, T)$ is the local equilibrium non-

Fig. 8. A simplified diagram of the experimental setup.

Table 5

Kinetic model parameters for Eq. (9). The parameters E_a and m were taken from the experimental kinetic model fit in Table 4, while n and k_0 were adjusted to best fit the experimental packed-bed results performed at a range of pressure.

E_a	84	[kJ mol ⁻¹]
k_0	5.3×10^4	[mol ⁻¹ m ³ s ⁻¹]
m	0.8	[-]
n	-0.6	[-]

stoichiometry, where the partial pressure is related to concentration by the ideal gas law $p_{O_2} = C_{O_2} RT$. A pressure dependence $\left(\frac{p}{p^0}\right)^n$, was added to the kinetic model. The pressure can affect the apparent intrinsic kinetics of the granules, because it affects the gas phase mass transport, with the diffusion coefficient scaling with the inverse of the pressure $D \propto \frac{1}{p}$. The parameters for Eq. (9) used in the simulations are given in Table 5.

It should be noted that in deriving Eq. (9) from the kinetic model fit in Eq. (6), the time differential of the local equilibrium non-stoichiometry $\delta_{eq}(p_{O_2}, T)$ was assumed to be zero. This assumes that the rate of change of the equilibrium is negligible relative to the rate of change of the non-stoichiometry δ due to the reaction.

The $t = 0$ boundary condition of the PDE was set to be the equilibrium oxygen concentration, which was calculated using the reduction non-stoichiometry δ_{rd} , and oxidation temperature T_{ox} ,

$$C_{O_2}(t = 0) = \frac{p_{O_2,eq}(\delta_{rd}, T_{ox})}{RT} \quad [\text{mol m}^{-3}] \quad (10)$$

The inflow boundary concentration of the bed was given by the incoming oxygen mole fraction and the reactor pressure,

$$C_{O_2}(x = 0) = x_{O_2,in} \frac{p_{ox}}{RT} \quad [\text{mol m}^{-3}]. \quad (11)$$

The superficial gas velocity u_s is derived from the reactor cross section A_{bed} and the gas volumetric flow rate v ,

$$u_s = \frac{v}{A_{bed}}. \quad (12)$$

The volumetric flow rate in the reactor v , was determined from the input flow rate defined at standard temperature and pressure $v_{s.t.p.}$, using the ideal gas law scaling relationship.

The time evolution of the system was then solved using a direct time stepping method, and a maximum step of $\Delta t = 1$ s.

4. Packed-bed reactor experiments

4.1. Experimental setup

A lab scale packed-bed reactor system (PID Eng&Tech MicroEffi, shown schematically in Fig. 8, was used to cycle the perovskite granules through the oxidation and reduction conditions as well as to control

Table 6

Parameters of the packed-bed reactor taken from the experiments, which were used to model the process. The bed void fraction was calculated by forming a bed with the same mass in a 10 mL graduated cylinder, used to measure the volume, and using the granule density from Table 2.

Bed length	L_{bed}	50	[mm]
Bed radius	R_{bed}	4.5	[mm]
Bed void fraction	ϵ_{bed}	0.437	[-]
Oxide mass	m_{SCF}	5.875	[g]
Oxide concentration	C_{SCF}	10339	[mol m ⁻³]
Reduction temperature	T_{red}	873	[K]
Reduction p_{O_2}	$p_{O_2,red}$	0.004	[bar]
Oxidation temperature	T_{ox}	598–648	[K]
Oxidation pressure	p_{ox}	1–10	[bar]
Oxidation x_{O_2}	$x_{O_2,in}$	0.004–0.016	-
Input flow rate	$v_{s.t.p.}$	0.161	[L min ⁻¹]

the flow and mixture of gasses into the packed-bed as seen in Fig. 8. Two gas bottles were connected to the systems via mass flow controllers (MFCs), nitrogen grade 5.0 and 10% oxygen in nitrogen. This combination allowed the system to flow gas mixtures with oxygen fractions in the range 0.4%–10% O₂. 5080 mg of Sr_{0.8}Ca_{0.2}FeO_{3-δ} granules were loaded into the stainless steel micro-reactor, making a packed-bed with specifications listed in Table 6. The tubular reactor is located inside a cylindrical electric furnace, with a thermocouple inside the bed for control feedback. The reactor can operate at an elevated pressure with an electronically controlled pressure regulator at the outlet. The exhaust of the system was connected to a Mesa Lambda-Sonde oxygen sensor, which is capable of measuring a wide range of oxygen concentrations from 20% down to 10⁻²⁶ %. The experimental procedure for a single cycle was made up of 5 steps:

- Reduction:** Heat granules from 623 K to 873 K with a heating rate of 10 K/min and held at 873 K for 70 min with a flow of 160 mL min⁻¹ of 0.4% O₂ in N₂.
- Cool Down:** Cool the reactor down from 873 K to 623 K with a cooling rate of 10 K/min without flow.
- Pressurisation:** Pressurise the bed with 160 mL min⁻¹ of N₂ to the desired oxidation pressure.
- Oxidation:** At 623 K flow 160 mL min⁻¹ of 0.4% O₂ in N₂ for 150 min.
- Gas Check:** Bypass the reactor with a flow of 160 mL min⁻¹ of 0.4% O₂ in N₂.

Step 5 allows the gas mixture to flow straight into the oxygen sensor with the reactor bypassed to measure the oxygen concentration of the in-flowing gas. In establishing the experimental procedure 10–15 cycles were completed, so that the results below are for already cycled granules.

Fig. 9. The oxygen impurity of the gas leaving the packed-bed in ppm vs. time, with the experimental results shown with solid lines and the model results with dashed lines. (a) Varying the oxidation pressure p_{ox} at fixed temperature $T_{\text{ox}} = 623$ K and input oxygen mole fraction $x_{\text{O}_2, \text{in}} = 0.004$. (b) Varying the input oxygen mole fraction $x_{\text{O}_2, \text{in}}$ at fixed oxidation temperature $T_{\text{ox}} = 623$ K and pressure $p_{\text{ox}} = 10$ bar. (c) Varying oxidation temperature T_{ox} at fixed pressure $p_{\text{ox}} = 10$ bar and input oxygen mole fraction $x_{\text{O}_2, \text{in}} = 0.004$. (d) A comparison of the $\text{Sr}_{0.8}\text{Ca}_{0.2}\text{FeO}_{3-\delta}$ packed-bed performance to an equal sized packed-bed of $\text{SrFeO}_{3-\delta}$.

4.2. Experiment results

The reduction conditions and the input gas flow rate were identical for every experiment as indicated in Table 6, with experiments performed at different oxidation temperatures T_{ox} , oxidation pressures p_{ox} , and input oxygen mole fractions $x_{\text{O}_2, \text{in}}$. The packed-bed performance for the experiments is visualised in Fig. 9 in terms of the oxygen impurity at the outlet vs. time. Initially the effect of the total pressure on the performance of the packed-bed during oxidation was investigated, and are shown in Fig. 9(a). It can be seen that both the lowest oxygen impurity and the duration of the low oxygen impurity phase both improve with increasing pressure. This strong dependence on the pressure is to be expected as the residence time is proportional to the pressure, allowing for more time for the deoxygenation reaction. Furthermore the increased p_{O_2} improves both the thermodynamic limit for oxygen storage capacity and should also improve the kinetic performance. For the oxidation at 10 bar, the reactor output had less than 10 ppm oxygen concentration for just over 80 min, giving 13 standard litres of purified N_2 .

Also shown in Fig. 9(a) are the results of the simulation of the packed-bed at the same conditions. The pressure dependence of the kinetic model in Eq. (9) of $\left(\frac{p}{p^\circ}\right)^n$ was adjusted to best fit the increasing oxygen ppm data towards the end of each oxidation, with $n = -0.6$ giving the best fit. This inverse pressure dependent term then slows the kinetic rate with increasing pressure, but overall the kinetic rate still increases with pressure as the oxygen concentration increases proportional to the pressure and overcompensates the $\left(\frac{p}{p^\circ}\right)^n$ in Eq. (9).

It is important to note that the lab-scale packed-bed is not capable of achieving the low oxygen impurities predicted by the model at the early stages of oxidation at elevated pressures. The experimental oxygen impurity measurements show a floor which decreases with

increasing pressure. This floor measurement is likely due to both trace oxygen leakage into the flow after the packed bed, and the fact that the experiment will not have ideal plug flow as assumed in the model. There would be preferential flow paths, particularly at the edges of the bed, as the granule diameters were on the order of 1 mm and the bed diameter is 9 mm. Trace oxygen leakage into the flow before and at the oxygen sensor is also very difficult to eliminate, due to the low oxygen partial pressures and the relatively low flow rates used in these experiments. These effects should be less pronounced in a larger scale packed-bed.

The effect of the oxygen input mole fraction $x_{\text{O}_2, \text{in}}$, is shown in Fig. 9(b), where it can be seen that the performance decreases with increasing oxygen mole fraction in the gas stream. Both the base purity and the duration of time at low ppm decrease, which is due to the larger quantity of oxygen to be absorbed. This could be compensated by using a larger packed-bed for longer residence times and greater oxygen storage capacity. The size of the bed should scale proportionately with $x_{\text{O}_2, \text{in}}$ to maintain similar performance. Again the model agrees well with the increasing oxygen impurity at the later stages of the experiment.

The effect of the oxidation temperature on the performance of the packed-bed is shown in Fig. 9(c). On this small-scale at 10 bar, the oxidation temperature of 623 K offered the best performance. At 598 K a slight improvement can be seen in lower output oxygen mole fraction, but the low ppm levels are maintained for a shorter time, likely due to slower kinetics. At higher temperatures, the kinetic rates increase, but at the cost of a smaller equilibrium bed capacity and a larger equilibrium oxygen partial pressure. The model agrees reasonably well with the tail end of the oxygen increase at both 623 K and 648 K, but greatly underestimates the performance at 598 K. The kinetics in the packed-bed could well be in a different rate limiting regime than the experiments performed in the TGA, due to the differences in contacting

Table 7

Parameters for the packed-bed simulation for 1000 N m³ h⁻¹ test case. The bed void space and oxide concentration match those of the experimental packed-bed.

Packed-bed parameters			
Bed length	L_{bed}	1.113	[mm]
Bed radius	R_{bed}	0.5	[mm]
Bed void fraction	ϵ_{bed}	0.437	[-]
Oxide mass	m_{SCF}	1629	[kg]
Oxide concentration	C_{SCF}	10 339	[mol m ⁻³]
Reduction temperature	T_{red}	873	[K]
Reduction p_{O_2}	$p_{\text{O}_2,\text{red}}$	0.004	[bar]
Oxidation temperature	T_{ox}	623	[K]
Oxidation pressure	p_{ox}	10	[bar]
Oxidation x_{O_2}	$x_{\text{O}_2,\text{in}}$	0.004	[-]
Input flow rate	$v_{\text{s,i,p}}$	1000	[N m ³ h ⁻¹]

and relative quantities of gas and solid. The kinetic could be corrected by adjusting the activation energy to a lower value. Here we did not do this, but instead assume that the model is relatively accurate at 623 K and perform a scaled up model at this temperature.

Finally, a packed-bed of SrFeO_{3-δ} granules was also tested, with the same number of moles of granules, giving a total mass of 6.20 g, and the same bed length as in Table 6. The packed-bed performance is compared to Sr_{0.8}Ca_{0.2}FeO_{3-δ} in Fig. 9(d), with a clear performance increase seen in the duration at low ppm levels for Sr_{0.8}Ca_{0.2}FeO_{3-δ}. This supports the material selection as we produce more purified nitrogen per cycle with a larger oxygen storage capacity. In practice this would allow for smaller reactors for a given capacity and cycle time.

Based on the performance of the lab-scale packed-bed, the oxidation processes conditions for a scaled up model were selected as an oxidation temperature of 623 K, at a pressure of 10 bar, with an oxygen mole fraction input of $x_{\text{O}_2,\text{in}} = 0.004$. The experimental results for oxidation at 598 K and 10 bar indicate that even lower temperature oxidation would be feasible, and perhaps more favourable for a scaled up application, but we restrict the further discussion to conditions where the model is most accurate.

5. Testcase

In this section we model an intermediate scale system for the production of 1000 N m³ h⁻¹ of purified N₂. A large bed diameter of 1 m was chosen to achieve a larger bed capacity and minimise the pressure drop across the bed to a minimum. A real system would include two identical reactors which would alternate between oxidation and reduction cycles to ensure constant N₂ production. A total cycle time of 10 h (oxidation time of 5 h for each reactor) was then specified to allow ample time for heating and regeneration. The packed-beds were assumed to have the same packing density as the packed-bed experiments, and the operating pressure of 10 bar was selected as it offered the best performance. The resulting packed-bed dimensions and simulation parameters are given in Table 7.

The packed-bed experiments were simulated for isothermal operation. In a larger scale packed-bed reactor, temperature control would require cooling the bed during oxidation. It would be more practical to perform the oxidation step in an adiabatic mode, where the heat of reaction would heat the bed and the flowing gas. This was included in the simulation by coupling the convection diffusion model to a heat transfer model of the form,

$$(\rho C_p)_{\text{eff}} \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + \rho_f C_{p,f} u_s \cdot \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} + k_{\text{eff}} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} = -\Delta h_{\text{O}}^{\circ} C_{\text{SCF}} \frac{\partial \delta}{\partial t} \quad (13)$$

where $(\rho C_p)_{\text{eff}}$ is the effective density and specific heat capacity of the packed-bed and gas phase, T is the local temperature, ρ_f and $C_{p,f}$ are the gas phase density and specific heat capacity respectively, u_s is the superficial velocity of the fluid, k_{eff} is the effective thermal conductivity of the packed-bed, $-\Delta h_{\text{O}}^{\circ} C_{\text{SCF}} \frac{\partial \delta}{\partial t}$ is the heat source term due to the

Fig. 10. A comparison of the output oxygen mole fraction ratios for isothermal and adiabatic reactor models. Results for $\delta(x,t)$, $x_{\text{O}_2}(x,T)$ and for the adiabatic case $T(x,t)$ are shown in figures S13 and S14 of the ESI.

oxidation reaction. Details on the packed-bed effective properties used are given in Section 7 of the ESI. The scaled up case was then simulated in both adiabatic and isothermal operation modes.

The output N₂ purity of the reactor model versus time is displayed in Fig. 10 for both model cases. The bed utilisation at the cut off oxygen concentration was 78.5% of the maximum oxygen capacity if the entire bed were oxidised to equilibrium. The result of the analysis of the test case reactor for isothermal and adiabatic operation confirm previous findings [10], that an adiabatic reactor can be assumed to operate approximately isothermally, where the heat of oxidation increases the reactor temperature by a maximum of 8 K, leading to very similar performance (see Figure S14 in the ESI). This small increase in temperature due to the reaction can also be seen in the output N₂ purity in Fig. 10, where a minor reduction in purity as well as bed capacity is visible in the adiabatic reactor versus the isothermal reactor.

5.1. Energy balance

The total energy demand for the testcase in the previous section is calculated according to the equation [10];

$$E_{\text{total}} = W_{\text{PSA}} + W_{\text{comp}} + W_{\text{vac}} + Q_{\text{gas,sens}} + Q_{\text{solid,sens}} + Q_{\text{red}} \quad [\text{J mol}^{-1} \text{N}_2] \quad (14)$$

where W_{PSA} is the energy demand of the PSA system, W_{comp} is energy demand of the compressor after the PSA, W_{vac} is the energy demand of the vacuum pump used to regenerate the beds, $Q_{\text{gas,sens}}$ is the sensible heat demand of the gas, $Q_{\text{solid,sens}}$ is the sensible heat demand of the solid, and Q_{red} is the heat demand of the reduction reaction used to regenerate the bed. The PSA energy demand is modelled according to the manufacturer data present in Fig. 1. The compressor after the PSA is treated as an adiabatic compression with an efficiency of 84%. The vacuum pump energy demand is modelled according to an analytical function [35]. The sensible heat for the incoming gas is assumed to be partially supplied via a heat exchanger with the outgoing N₂, with heat exchanger efficiency of 85%. The sensible heating of the solid and the heat required for the reduction reaction are not considered to be recovered in the process. Full details of each energy demand component are provided in the ESI.

The energy demand of the testcase calculated according to Eq. (14) is plotted in the left side of Fig. 11. Also shown is the energy demand of using PSA alone to provide the same purity of N₂ with compression after the PSA from 7 to 10 bar. The approximate energy demand of cryogenic air separation for N₂ production at the same scale of 1000 N m³ h⁻¹, calculated according to the data in Fig. 1. The energy balance of the PSA plus redox system for the simulated testcase gives a total energy

Fig. 11. Left: A visual break-down of the energy demand of the nitrogen production process for nitrogen supplied at 10 bar with an oxygen cut-off impurity of 3 ppm. Energy requirement is split into heat and work (electricity). Right: The capacity vs. purity plot (Fig. 2) including the testcase combined PSA and redox unit.

demand of $E_{\text{total}} = 26.2 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1} \text{ N}_2$. This add on redox unit requires $E_{\text{redox}} = 4.3 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1} \text{ N}_2$, most of which is heat, while the PSA unit has an energy demand of $W_{\text{PSA}} = 21.8 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1} \text{ N}_2$.

The results of the energy demand calculations compare very well with the energy demand of a PSA unit alone, which would be much higher at $W_{\text{PSA-alone}} = 108 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1} \text{ N}_2$. The energy demand also compares well with the small-scale cryogenic air separation units that require between 20 and 25 $\text{kJ mol}^{-1} \text{ N}_2$ of electricity. Furthermore, the combined PSA and redox process offers greatly improved capacity at high purities relative to a PSA system alone, as can be seen in the right side of Fig. 11. This could effectively extend the useable range of PSA systems to overlap those of cryogenic systems. The benefits of this process are far more pronounced than we determined in a previous study [10]. In this previous work the energy demand of PSA systems was taken from Krenzke et al. [36], which appears to greatly underestimated the energy demand shown here (see ESI Section 1 for more details).

Here we focus on a large-scale system of $1000 \text{ N m}^3 \text{ h}^{-1} \text{ N}_2$, but the general processes idea could be applied to improve the energy demand and capacity at low oxygen impurities for PSA systems of all sizes. At smaller scales one could also design the process to use a single packed-bed redox reactor and a buffer tank. This process could then offer a broader range of application for on-site N_2 production using PSA.

6. Conclusions

There is a significant technology gap in terms of capacity, purity and energy demand, between pressure swing adsorption systems and cryogenic air separation systems for the production of high-purity N_2 . In this work we investigated the performance of an add on redox unit for the separation of trace oxygen as a means of significantly improving the capacity and purity range of pressure swing adsorption systems. The results indicate that this method is technically feasible and can indeed offer high capacity and high-purity with a favourable energy demand. Furthermore, the perovskite oxide $\text{Sr}_{0.8}\text{Ca}_{0.2}\text{FeO}_{3-\delta}$ is identified as a very promising candidate material for oxygen separation processes.

7. Nomenclature

δ	[-]	Oxygen non-stoichiometry
T	[K]	Temperature
p	[bar]	Absolute pressure
p°	[bar]	Reference pressure (1 bar)
p_{O_2}	[bar]	Oxygen partial pressure
δ_{eq}	[-]	Equilibrium oxygen non-stoichiometry
δ_0	[-]	Initial oxygen non-stoichiometry

ρ_{SCF}	$[\text{kg m}^{-3}]$	Material density of $\text{Sr}_{0.8}\text{Ca}_{0.2}\text{FeO}_{3-\delta}$
ρ_{granule}	$[\text{kg m}^{-3}]$	Density of $\text{Sr}_{0.8}\text{Ca}_{0.2}\text{FeO}_{3-\delta}$ granules
$\epsilon_{\text{granule}}$	[-]	Granule void space fraction
ϵ_{bed}	[-]	Packed-bed free volume fraction
X	[-]	Conversion extent
k_0	$[\text{mol}^{-1} \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}]$	Kinetic rate constant
E_a	$[\text{kJ mol}^{-1}]$	Apparent activation energy
m	[-]	Conversion extent power dependence
n	[-]	Pressure power dependence
C_{O_2}	$[\text{mol m}^{-3}]$	Oxygen concentration
C_{SCF}	$[\text{mol m}^{-3}]$	$\text{Sr}_{0.8}\text{Ca}_{0.2}\text{FeO}_{3-\delta}$ concentration
u_s	$[\text{m s}^{-1}]$	Superficial gas flow velocity
D_{eff}	$[\text{m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}]$	Effective diffusion coefficient
L_{bed}	[m]	Length of the packed-bed
R_{bed}	[m]	Radius of the packed-bed
m_{SCF}	[kg]	Oxide mass in the packed-bed
x_{O_2}	[-]	Oxygen mole fraction
$x_{\text{O}_2, \text{in}}$	[-]	Oxygen mole fraction in the input flow
v	$[\text{m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}]$	Volume flow rate in the reactor
$v_{\text{s.t.p.}}$	$[\text{m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}]$	Input volume flow rate at 300 K and 1 bar

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary material related to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2022.139289>.

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